

Integrated image analysis and statistical modeling for the morphological characterization of porous microstructures

Análise de imagens e modelagem estatística integradas para a caracterização morfológica de microestruturas porosas

Análisis de imágenes y modelado estadístico integrado para la caracterización morfológica de microestructuras porosas

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a methodology for the quantitative and spatial characterization of porous materials, grounded in digital image-processing techniques (DIP) and statistical modelling. The proposal stems from the need for methods that are more accessible, scalable, and reproducible than traditional porosimetry and micro-CT approaches. To this end, three-dimensional image sets obtained via X-ray micro-computed tomography are employed. The primary objective is to accurately quantify total porosity, map its spatial distribution, and analyze microstructural descriptors such as connectivity, anisotropy, tortuosity, and pore-size distribution. The workflow integrates pre-processing, binarization with multiple techniques (Otsu, Sauvola, and K-means), morphological operations, and statistical evaluation of the porosity models. Additionally, polynomial regressions and normality tests are applied to assess porosity profiles along the Z-axis. Results reveal significant heterogeneity in porosity and connectivity among the samples, underscoring the importance of a multiscale approach. Evaluated in light of the literature, the methodology shows that outcomes are strongly influenced by the chosen segmentation method and the number of morphological operations applied, yet it provides a faithful representation of porous structures for flow, filtration, and energy-related modelling applications.

Keywords: Porosity. Image Processing. Microstructure. Statistical Modeling. Morphological Analysis.

RESUMO

Este estudo apresenta uma metodologia para a caracterização quantitativa e espacial de materiais porosos, baseada em técnicas de processamento digital de imagens (PDI) e em modelagem estatística. A proposta surge da necessidade de métodos mais acessíveis, escaláveis e reprodutíveis em comparação às abordagens tradicionais de porosimetria e microtomografia. Para tanto, utilizam-se conjuntos de imagens tridimensionais obtidas por microtomografia de raios X. O objetivo central é quantificar com precisão a porosidade total, mapear sua distribuição espacial e analisar descritores microestruturais, tais como conectividade, anisotropia, tortuosidade e distribuição dos tamanhos de poro. O fluxo de trabalho combina etapas de pré-processamento, binarização por

múltiplas técnicas (Otsu, Sauvola e K-means), operações morfológicas e avaliação estatística dos modelos de porosidade. Adicionalmente, aplicam-se regressões polinomiais e testes de normalidade para avaliar os perfis de porosidade ao longo do eixo Z. Os resultados revelam heterogeneidade significativa na porosidade e na conectividade das amostras, ressaltando a importância da abordagem multiescalar. A metodologia, avaliada à luz da literatura, evidencia que os resultados dependem fortemente do método de segmentação escolhido e do número de operações morfológicas empregadas, proporcionando, contudo, uma representação fiel das estruturas porosas para modelagens de escoamento, filtração e aplicações energéticas.

Palavras-chave: Porosidade. Processamento de Imagens. Microestrutura. Modelagem Estatística. Análise Morfológica.

RESUMEN

Este estudio presenta una metodología para la caracterización cuantitativa y espacial de materiales porosos, basada en técnicas de procesamiento digital de imágenes (PDI) y en modelado estadístico. La propuesta surge de la necesidad de métodos más accesibles, escalables y reproducibles en comparación con los enfoques tradicionales de porosimetría y microtomografía. Para ello, se utilizan conjuntos de imágenes tridimensionales obtenidas mediante microtomografía de rayos X. El objetivo central es cuantificar con precisión la porosidad total, cartografiar su distribución espacial y analizar descriptores microestructurales tales como conectividad, anisotropía, tortuosidad y distribución de tamaños de poro. El flujo de trabajo combina fases de preprocesamiento, binarización mediante múltiples técnicas (Otsu, Sauvola y K-means), operaciones morfológicas y evaluación estadística de los modelos de porosidad. Además, se aplican regresiones polinómicas y pruebas de normalidad para evaluar los perfiles de porosidad a lo largo del eje Z. Los resultados revelan una heterogeneidad significativa en la porosidad y la conectividad de las muestras, resaltando la importancia del enfoque multiescalar. La metodología, evaluada a la luz de la literatura, muestra que los resultados dependen en gran medida del método de segmentación elegido y del número de operaciones morfológicas empleadas; no obstante, proporciona una representación fiel de las estructuras porosas para modelos de flujo, filtración y aplicaciones energéticas.

Palabras clave: Porosidad. Procesamiento de Imágenes. Microestructura. Modelado Estadístico. Análisis Morfológico.

1 INTRODUCTION

Granular porous materials, such as sedimentary rocks and artificial media modeled by sphere packings, play fundamental roles in diverse applications, particularly in filtration processes, enhanced oil recovery (EOR), percolation

studies, and understanding transport phenomena in geological media (Lao *et al.*, 2024). Their intrinsic structural properties including porosity, connectivity, tortuosity, and pore size distribution directly influence critical macroscopic properties such as permeability, effective diffusion, and mechanical strength (Xiao *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, the precise characterization of the porous microstructure is essential for predicting functional performance and optimizing practical applications.

Traditionally, structural analysis of these materials has employed techniques like mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP), gas adsorption by Brunauer–Emmett–Teller method (BET method), and X-ray computed microtomography (μ CT-RX). While providing valuable data, these approaches exhibit significant limitations, including high dependency on theoretical models (especially MIP and BET), high cost (high-resolution μ CT-RX), and constraints regarding spatial resolution or volumetric representativeness (Yang *et al.*, 2024; Yu, B. *et al.*, 2022). In this context, digital image processing (DIP)-based techniques emerge as promising alternatives for the direct and quantitative extraction of morphological parameters from two-dimensional images (Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)) or three-dimensional images (μ CT-RX data) of rock samples and granular assemblies.

The use of DIP, combined with robust statistical methods, enables detailed quantification of internal morphology, emphasizing parameters such as pore/grain size and shape distribution, connectivity, structural anisotropy and number of connected components (Sarkar *et al.*, 2025). These methods allow for the analysis of large data volumes in an automated, objective, and highly reproducible manner, while also generating intuitive visual representations that facilitate qualitative and quantitative interpretation of results.

Despite these advances, studies that systematically integrate advanced digital segmentation techniques, mathematical morphology analysis, and spatial statistical modelling to characterize complex porous materials, such as heterogeneous rocks and sphere columns with different packing arrangements, remain scarce (Cao *et al.*, 2024). A gap exists in the literature regarding the combined application of these tools to quantitatively and explicitly investigate the

topological and geometric aspects of porosity in systems with heterogeneous feature distributions, as is common in geological samples and granular media (Cao *et al.*, 2024).

Given this context, and utilizing three-dimensional image datasets acquired via μ CT-RX, this work aims to perform a quantitative and spatially resolved characterization of porous microstructures, employing these representative images of rocks and percolation columns composed of spheres. The proposed approach is based on DIP techniques applied to the μ CT-RX data and statistical modelling, aiming to: (i) quantify the global average porosity; (ii) evaluate the spatial distribution of porosity along specific axes; (iii) determine metrics of connectivity, anisotropy, and tortuosity; and (iv) statistically analyze the morphology and size distribution of pores or interstitial voids. The obtained results contribute to a deeper understanding of the internal structure of the investigated materials and provide essential insights for future applications in computational flow and transport modelling, as well as in the optimization of functional properties.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Porous materials are ubiquitous across a wide range of natural and engineered systems, playing a crucial role in key processes such as fluid transport, energy storage, thermal exchange, and heterogeneous chemical reactions. Sedimentary rocks, in particular, are composed of intricate networks of interconnected pores whose geometric and topological characteristics, including porosity, connectivity, tortuosity, and pore size distribution, directly influence macroscopic properties such as permeability, effective diffusivity, and mechanical strength (Xiao *et al.*, 2023).

Over recent decades, the quantitative characterization of porous microstructures has relied primarily on conventional laboratory techniques such as MIP, gas adsorption using the BET method, and μ CT-RX. While these techniques have provided valuable data, they are not without significant limitations. MIP and BET, for instance, are heavily dependent on simplifying

theoretical models and offer no spatially resolved insights. μ CT-RX, although capable of providing three-dimensional structural detail, is constrained by high equipment costs and limitations in volumetric representativeness due to resolution–scale trade-offs (Yang *et al.*, 2024; Yu, B. *et al.*, 2022).

In this context, DIP techniques have emerged as promising alternatives for the direct and quantitative morphological characterization of porous media. DIP allows for the automated and reproducible extraction of structural parameters from 2D or 3D image datasets, including petrographic thin sections, SEM images, or volumetric data from μ CT-RX scans (Liu *et al.*, 2024; Qin *et al.*, 2021).

Among the structural parameters accessible via DIP, key metrics include global porosity, pore size and shape distribution, structural anisotropy indices, the number of connected components and tortuosity (Sarkar *et al.*, 2025). These descriptors not only enable geometrical and topological descriptions of the pore space, but also serve as essential inputs for computational models of flow and mass transport in porous media. Such applications span multiple disciplines from geosciences and petroleum engineering to biomedical domains, including studies of trabecular bone and bioinspired porous scaffolds (Wenran *et al.*, 2025).

Furthermore, the integration of open-source computational libraries such as PoreSpy, scikit-image, and OpenCV into Python-based programming environments has facilitated the development of robust analytical workflow for segmentation, morphological analysis, and statistical modeling of porous microstructures. Binarization methods such as Otsu's thresholding, Sauvola's adaptive method, and k-means clustering are employed to accurately segment the solid and void phases of the material (Chengzhen *et al.*, 2025). Three-dimensional morphological operations including dilation, erosion, opening, and closing, provide insights into structural robustness and connectivity, while statistical tools such as the two-point correlation function and anisotropy index allow for the quantitative assessment of spatial organization (Chirol *et al.*, 2021; Rueden *et al.*, 2022).

Despite recent advances, current literature rarely integrates advanced segmentation algorithms, mathematical morphology, and spatial statistical modeling to systematically characterize complex heterogeneous porous

structures, like carbonate rocks or granular columns with variable packing (Cao *et al.*, 2024; Ziganshin *et al.*, 2023). Specifically, there's a significant gap in using these combined tools to resolve both the geometric and topological aspects of porosity in systems with strong local heterogeneity, a common feature in both geological formations and artificial granular media.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 SAMPLES AND ENVIRONMENT PREPARATION AND PREPROCESSING

Four porous media Samples—A), B), C), and D) (Figure 1)—were analyzed. Samples A) and D) were columns packed with glass beads (4mm for A), and a 3mm/4mm mix for D), sourced from Silva's 2024 porous media study. Meanwhile, Samples B) and C) were rock samples from the X-ray Computed Tomography Laboratory at the Federal University of Pernambuco's Department of Nuclear Energy.

Figure 1. Samples A) 4mm pebble Glass, B) rock type X, C) rock type Y, D) mixed pebble glass (3mm and 4mm).

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The methodology was implemented in a Python environment, leveraging specialized libraries for image analysis, numerical processing, and graphical visualization. Key libraries included PoreSpy for characterizing porous microstructures, scikit-image for filtering, segmentation, and morphological operations, and OpenCV (Li; Asbjörnsson; Lindqvist, 2021) for adaptive contrast equalization. Additionally, NumPy was used for 3D array manipulation, SciPy for spatial filtering and transform operations, matplotlib, seaborn, and Plotly handled

the graphical visualization. To ensure visual reproducibility and quality in the presentation of results, graphical parameters were configured to standardize styles, color palettes, fonts, and resolutions. A perceptually uniform color palette was implemented using the seaborn library (Kochukrishnan *et al.*, 2024), and plots were optimized for publications through predefined DPI settings, figure dimensions, refined gridlines, and typographic styles compatible with PDF outputs.

The process commenced with the loading of 2D image datasets acquired in .tiff format, representing sequential slices of a three-dimensional porous material sample. The images were systematically organized in dedicated directories and loaded using a custom-adapted implementation of the scikit-image library's "imread_collection" function. To ensure computational efficiency and complexity management, a maximum limit of 300 images per dataset was imposed. During loading, fundamental metadata were extracted, including total image count, slice dimensions (height and width), data type (dtype), and minimum/maximum grayscale intensity values.

Preprocessing of the three-dimensional image volumes involved an advanced operational sequence focused on standardization and enhancement of relevant morphological features. Initially, 3D median filtering (Zou; Yao; Wang, 2021) was applied for noise reduction, effectively smoothing abrupt variations while preserving structural boundaries. Subsequently, illumination correction was performed using a large-scale Gaussian filter ($\sigma = 50$) (Lei *et al.*, 2022), enabling background variation compensation and intensity normalization across all planes.

The following stage employed CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization) (Chen; Liang, 2024) via the OpenCV library to implement adaptive histogram equalization for each 2D slice. This approach enhances local contrast, particularly in regions exhibiting low intensity variation. This step plays a critical role in differentiating between solid and void regions, thereby facilitating subsequent segmentation and quantitative analysis stages.

3.2 BINARIZATION OF IMAGES

After preprocessing, the three-dimensional image volumes underwent binarization, a crucial step for distinguishing between the solid and porous phases of the sample. To ensure accurate segmentation of regions of interest, three distinct approaches were employed, each offering varying levels of complexity and spatial sensitivity. The first method applied was Otsu's technique, a global thresholding approach effective for images with well-defined contrast, though limited in cases with local intensity variations (Yu *et al.*, 2025).

To overcome these limitations, an adaptive thresholding strategy based on Sauvola's method was adopted, which calculates thresholds locally and proved robust in segmenting regions with subtle illumination gradients (Bipin Nair; Anusha; Anusha, 2022). Additionally, a clustering-based method using K-means was implemented. As an unsupervised segmentation technique, K-means classifies image pixels into porous and solid phases based on statistical similarity, offering greater flexibility in identifying poorly defined phase boundaries and contributing to a more accurate representation of the microstructure (Tabianan; Velu; Ravi, 2022).

Each method was independently applied to the 3D volume, generating three distinct binarized representations of the sample, as exemplified in Figure 2 for Sample A. The original slices exhibit visible noise, a common artifact in μ CT images.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

To determine the most suitable binarization for quantitative characterization, an objective metric based on edge contrast was implemented.

This utilized the Canny edge detector (Ge *et al.*, 2022) applied to a central slice of the binarized volume. The metric calculates the mean intensity difference between regions adjacent to identified edges, with higher contrast values indicating superior separation between solid and porous phases.

The three binarization approaches (Otsu, Sauvola, and K-means) underwent quantitative evaluation using this contrast metric. The method yielding the highest contrast value was then automatically selected as the primary binarized representation for subsequent spatial, morphological, and statistical analysis stages.

This evaluation strategy provides a systematic and reproducible framework for selecting the most effective method, minimizing subjectivity while ensuring the binarization accurately represents the sample's porous structures.

3.3 SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF MICROSTRUCTURE

Spatial characterization of the porous microstructure was conducted using quantitative metrics applied to the pre-selected binarized volume. This aimed to evaluate porosity distribution, spatial connectivity, and morphological variability along the three principal axes (X, Y, and Z). To visualize the 3D distribution of the porous phase, porosity maps projected onto the XY, XZ, and YZ planes were generated by averaging corresponding orthogonal slices. Beyond visualization, the standard deviation of porosity was calculated per plane to measure spatial heterogeneity; higher values indicated increased variability in pore distribution and suggested regions with significantly differing pore densities, aiding in identifying structural anisotropies and internal morphological gradients.

The two-point correlation function was employed, utilizing the PoreSpy library (Qin *et al.*, 2021), to quantify the spatial dependence of pore presence at different positions. This function represents the probability that, given a point in the porous phase, another point at a specified distance will also belong to the same phase. While in homogeneous materials the function converges to the square of the mean porosity as distance increases, organized structures show slower decay and distinct peaks, allowing inference of structural organization,

connectivity, and sample isotropy. Pore size distribution analysis was primarily conducted using PoreSpy's "pore_size_distribution" function, which estimates equivalent pore radii via morphological transformations.

As an alternative for insufficient data, a complementary technique based on scikit-image's regionprops function (Kuwahara *et al.*, 2023) calculated the equivalent area of 3D-labeled pores, converting them to size estimates and generating normalized histograms. This dual-methodology approach ensures analytical flexibility, enabling characterization of both well-defined structures and materials with irregular or fragmented pores.

3.4 MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

Morphological analysis aimed to investigate the structural robustness, sensitivity to local modifications, and topological connectivity of the porous phase. Classical mathematical morphology operations were applied to the binarized volume using a three-dimensional neighborhood structuring element.

Four fundamental morphological operations were applied: dilation, erosion, opening, and closing. All were implemented using the SciPy library (Rueden *et al.*, 2022) and applied three-dimensionally to the volume. A unit-radius three-dimensional sphere (3D ball) served as the isotropic structuring element to define local neighborhood connectivity for each voxel.

Dilation adds voxels to the porous region, expanding existing pores. Erosion removes peripheral voxels, shrinking pores and disconnecting fragile structures. Opening (erosion followed by dilation) eliminates small isolated regions or noise. Closing (dilation followed by erosion) fills small cavities and connects adjacent pores (Chirol *et al.*, 2021).

These operations were applied iteratively, up to six times, allowing us to observe how structural properties evolved with increasing morphological transformation. For each iteration, two primary metrics were calculated: porosity, defined as the fraction of porous voxels relative to the total volume, and connectivity, estimated by counting connected components using 3D labeling with second-order connectivity (Liu, Pengcheng; Shao; Xiao, 2024). From these

measurements, evolution curves for both porosity and connectivity were generated, clearly revealing the structure's response to the controlled topological modifications.

Interpretation of the observed patterns enables identification of the pore network's perturbation sensitivity: for example, an abrupt connectivity decline during successive erosions may indicate a highly fragmented structure or one vulnerable to compression. Conversely, connectivity increases following closing operations may suggest the presence of nearly connected channels that become integrated through minor modifications. This morphological analysis provides an additional perspective for porous characterization, allowing inference of implicit mechanical properties, structural robustness, and fluid transport potential from simple geometric transformations.

3.5 ADVANCED CONNECTIVITY ANALYSIS

To understand the structural complexity and interconnectivity of the porous network, a detailed 3D analysis was performed, incorporating metrics like tortuosity, anisotropy, and topology. This analysis helps infer functional properties such as fluid transport, diffusion, and structural resistance.

The process began with 3D pore labeling using SciPy's label function with second-order connectivity (26 neighbors), identifying each connected pore as a distinct component. Subsequently, the size distribution of these connected components (measured in voxel count) was characterized using descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, and percentiles. This approach allowed for assessing morphological diversity and identifying dominant flow channels, isolated structures, or extreme pore dimensions.

Pore network tortuosity was then estimated as the ratio between the effective transport path length and the straight-line distance along the Z-direction, utilizing the Euclidean Distance Transform (EDT) to identify the innermost points at the sample's inlet and outlet. The actual path length was determined as the maximum distance along the distance transform, representing the effective length for fluid traversal.

Tortuosity (τ) was then calculated as the ratio of these two measures, as given by Equation 1.

$$\tau = \frac{\text{Actual Path}}{\text{Straight-Line Distance}} \quad (1)$$

τ values approaching 1 indicate direct and efficient pathways, while higher values reveal complex, tortuous trajectories.

The structural anisotropy of the porous phase was evaluated through principal component analysis (PCA). Initially, the coordinates of voxels classified as porous were extracted, and the data were centered relative to the distribution centroid. The three-dimensional covariance matrix was subsequently computed from these centered coordinates. Following this, the matrix eigenvalues were obtained through spectral decomposition. The ratio between the largest (γ_{max}) and smallest eigenvalues (γ_{min}) served as the anisotropy index, as expressed by Equation 2.

$$\text{Anisotropy} = \frac{\gamma_{max}}{\gamma_{min}} \quad (2)$$

This index quantifies the degree of preferential orientation within the porous structure: values approaching 1 indicate isotropy (equitable distribution along axes), while elevated values suggest pronounced microstructural directionality.

3.6 ADVANCED STATISTICAL MODELING

To deepen the statistical understanding of porosity distribution throughout the sample, an advanced statistical analysis was performed based on statistical moments, normality tests, and polynomial model fitting. This approach enables rigorous investigation of porosity's spatial behavior, identifying systematic patterns or structural variations.

The porosity profile, extracted along the Z-axis as the porous fraction in each volume slice, underwent a comprehensive statistical analysis. Classical statistical moments were calculated to characterize the profile's distribution. These included the Mean, representing the average porosity value; Variance and Standard Deviation, which quantify the dispersion and variability of the profile; Skewness, indicating the degree of asymmetry in the distribution relative to its mean; and Kurtosis, measuring the concentration of values around the mean, reflecting the distribution's peakiness or flatness.

Furthermore, to assess the normality of the porosity profile, two specific tests were applied. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used due to its sensitivity to normality, particularly in smaller sample sizes. Additionally, the D'Agostino-Pearson test was employed, which combines measures of skewness and kurtosis to effectively evaluate deviations from a normal distribution.

The test results, comprising test statistics and p-values, were used to evaluate the profile's adherence to a normal distribution, guiding interpretation of subsequent fitting models.

To investigate systematic trends throughout the volume, a polynomial model of degree up to three was fitted to the porosity profile. The fitting procedure employed NumPy's polyfit function, generating a model of the form shown in Equation 3.

$$Y_z = a_0 + a_1 \cdot z_1 + a_2 \cdot z_2 + a_3 \cdot z_3 \quad (3)$$

where:

z represents the slice index along the Z-axis, Y_z is the estimated porosity.

Model fit quality was assessed through the coefficient of determination (R^2), which quantifies the proportion of variance explained by the model. R^2 values approaching 1 indicate strong correlation between the fitted model and observed data.

Additionally, residual analysis was performed to verify the randomness of deviations between observed and fitted values. The absence of systematic patterns in the residuals reinforces model validity and indicates that unexplained variability is random in nature.

This modeling provides a functional representation of porosity variation throughout the sample, enabling identification of potential gradients, transition zones, or anomalous regions that may directly impact the material's functional properties.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysis of the processed 3D images revealed significant variations in average porosity across all four samples. Sample C exhibited the lowest mean porosity (25.03 %), followed by Sample B (35.15 %) and Sample A (41.7 %), whereas Sample D showed the highest value (43.81 %). Otsu's segmentation was chosen because it achieved the highest edge-contrast index, computed as the mean absolute gray-level difference between regions adjacent to Canny-detected edges, indicating the best separation between solid and porous phases according to our objective metric. These porosity values were obtained using the Otsu method, where the highest value was obtained from the Canny function, a function used as a selection criterion.

The spatial analysis of porosity based on 2D projections revealed significant internal heterogeneity across all samples. Porosity maps generated in the XY, XZ, and YZ planes (Figures 3–6) displayed mean values consistent with global porosity estimates. However, the degree of variability—quantified by the standard deviation—differed across directions. The vertical planes (XZ and YZ) exhibited greater fluctuations in porosity, suggesting anisotropic microstructural organization likely associated with directional packing or sedimentation effects. In these visualizations, bright tones correspond to regions with higher solid content, while darker areas indicate greater porosity.

Figure 3. 3D porosity maps of Sample A, bright tones correspond to regions with higher solid content.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Figure 4. 3D porosity maps of Sample B, bright tones correspond to regions with higher solid content.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Figure 5. 3D porosity maps of Sample C, bright tones correspond to regions with higher solid content.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Figure 6. 3D porosity maps of Sample D, bright tones correspond to regions with higher solid content.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Analysis of porous structure connectivity, crucial for fluid transport, revealed considerable variation among the four samples: Sample C exhibited 242,014 connected components, Sample A had 3,708, Sample D displayed 49,084, and Sample B contained 36,396. Tortuosity along the Z-axis was 1.012 for Sample C, 1.047 for Sample A, 1.098 for Sample D, and 1.029 for Sample B, reflecting slight variations in flow pathway complexity in accordance with each sample's microstructure. Structural anisotropy varied from 1.081 in Sample A, 3.486 in Sample B, and 5.344 in Sample D up to 9.131 in Sample C, confirming directional architectures that favor transport along specific orientations (Xiao *et al.*, 2023). Mean sphericity, 0.932 in Sample B, 0.860 in Sample C, 0.861 in Sample D, and 0.860 in Sample A, further underscores differences in pore shape uniformity across the samples. Even with high connectivity, irregular pore distribution and pronounced anisotropy can complicate accurate transport behavior predictions in computational simulations like CFD.

Advanced statistical tools provided in-depth analysis of porosity distribution. Normality tests (Shapiro-Wilk and D'Agostino-Pearson) rejected the null hypothesis of normal distribution for all samples (p -values < 0.05), a finding that contrasts with Yang's observations (Yang *et al.*, 2024) regarding the stochastic nature of geological samples. Further, skewness coefficients (ranging from -1.535 to -0.419) indicated a predominance of smaller pores, resulting in a left-tailed distribution, while kurtosis values (-0.742 to 3.457) showed varying pore concentration around the mean, reflecting the diverse pore shapes and sizes within the samples (Figure 7). The Quantile-Quantile (Q-Q) plots (Figure 8)

visually supported these findings, highlighting significant deviations from the expected normality, especially evident at distribution tails.

Figure 7. Analyses of skewness and kurtosis to Samples A), B), C) and D).

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Figure 8. Evaluation of the normality of porosity distributions using Quantile-Quantile (Q-Q) plots.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Statistical modeling of porosity along the Z-axis, using a third-degree polynomial, yielded low coefficients of determination ($R^2 = 0.092$ and 0.481). This suggests the model inadequately explains porosity's spatial variability, indicating a dominance of random factors or complex geometric influences, consistent with

Yu *et al.* (2022) who advocate for spatial statistics and machine learning for nonlinear patterns in porous structures.

A morphological evaluation using dilation, erosion, opening, and closing operations revealed porosity changes consistent with literature: dilation increased porosity, while erosion significantly reduced it, highlighting structural fragility (Figure 9). Connectivity was also affected, particularly by opening operations, which fragmented continuous porous structures. These observations reinforce morphological analysis as a valuable tool for simulating physical processes like sintering, dissolution, and pore blockage, as noted by Sarkar *et al.* (2025).

The results obtained were compared with analogous studies that employed X-ray microtomography and digital image processing techniques. In particular, the works of Lao (Lao *et al.*, 2024) and Cao (Cao, Danping; Hou; Hou, 2024) reported similar values of anisotropy and tortuosity in packed sphere columns, as well as asymmetric porosity distributions. The strong agreement between the results presented here and the literature reinforces the validity of the methodology employed, both in the processing stage and in the morphostatistical quantification.

Figure 9. Porosity changes in Samples A), B), C), and D) due to morphological operations.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

5 CONCLUSION

This work proposed a methodology for the quantitative and spatial analysis of porous materials using digital image processing and statistical modeling. The workflow allowed extraction of key descriptors, such as porosity, connectivity, tortuosity, anisotropy, and pore size distribution, from μ CT-RX datasets in an automated and reproducible way. The preprocessing steps and segmentation methods, especially adaptive enhancement and thresholding, were effective in

highlighting porous structures. Among the binarization techniques, Otsu's method provided the best results based on the contrast evaluation.

Morphological operations revealed how structural features change under topological transformations, while connectivity analyses showed the complex nature of the pore networks. Tortuosity and anisotropy metrics provided insights into directional flow and structure orientation. Statistical analysis of porosity profiles showed spatial heterogeneity and limited model fit, indicating complex internal variation rather than smooth gradients.

Overall, the proposed framework offers a detailed and spatially resolved approach to porous structure characterization, particularly useful for flow modeling and material optimization. Future work may extend the method to more heterogeneous samples and integrate machine learning to enhance segmentation and predictive modeling.

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